

Design and Fabrication of Dryer for Zeolite Synthesis: Engineering Solution for Enhanced Material Processing

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Article History:

Received: 27.12.2024 Revised: 19.01.2025 Accepted: 23.01.2025 Published: 27.01.2025

ABSTRACT:

The design and fabrication of the electric dryer from locally sourced materials represent a cutting-edge advancement in drying technology, harnessing the unique properties of Zeolite materials to enhance energy efficiency and performance. Zeolites are microporous, aluminosilicate minerals known for their high adsorption capacity and thermal stability. Drying is one operation required in Zeolite synthesis and as a developing Nation, there is need to invest in design and fabrication of dryers instead of relying on the traditional method of drying where the Zeolite are allowed to dry natural in open air. The Electric dryer is engineered to provide precise temperature and speed control, uniform heat distribution and efficient air circulation thereby enhancing drying efficiency, reducing operational costs and promoting local technology. The dryer consists of a mild steel chamber, heating element, fan, thermocouple, temperature and speed control system. The fabrication process involved machining, welding and assembly of the various components. The dryer performance was evaluated by drying Kaolin (a precursor for Zeolite synthesis) samples under a certain temperature and fan speed to obtain percentage reduction in moisture content to 20% from 60%. The temperature range of the dryer is 28 to 300 degrees Celsius, dimensions of the designed and fabricated dryer are Width of 0.2286m, Height of 0.3048m and Breadth/depth of 0.3048m, Volume of dryer is $0.02124m^3$, Insulation thickness is 0.04m. while area of dryer door is $0.110 m^2$. For panel dimension: Height is 0.254m, Width is 0.152m and area of panel is $0.0386m^2$, Tray Dimension is 0.241m by 0.330m and area of tray $0.0795m^2$. Standard Operating Procedure and maintenance of the electric dryer was also captured in this work. The regulation of the fan speed is a novel approach to our design. This innovation represents a significant leap in the development of energy-efficient dryer, promising enhanced performance and reduced environmental impact.

Keywords: Aluminosilicate, Design, Engineered, Synthesis, Zeolite.

Suggested Citation: N.C. Egwu, B. Rasheed, M.C. Victor, " Design and Fabrication of Dryer for Zeolite Synthesis: Engineering Solution for Enhanced Material Processing," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(1), pp. 76-86, Jan-Feb 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(1).06

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INTRODUCTION

The electric dryer is the equipment for the removal of moisture from solids by forced ventilation while applying heat [1,2]. The dryer dimension and component were designed as shown in Figure 1 with principle of drying highlighted also in Figure 2. The materials used for the casing of the cabinet was made of mild steel sheet. The cabinet has a drying chamber with two trays. Heating element was installed at the top in the drying chamber.

At the top of the dryer was the fan, designed for the airflow in the chamber, the air flows through the electrical heating element and out via the holes by the left of the equipment.

In order to reduce heat loss, the casing was insulated [3]. The specification of the dryer are width: 0.2286 m, height: 0.3048 m, breadth/depth: 0.3048 m, volume: 0.02124 m^3 and the insulation thickness is 0.04 m

Dryer door dimension is width: 0.305 m, height: 0.361 m and area: 0.110 m^2 .

Figure 1. Dryer Design
Source: [4]

Figure 2. Basic Principle of the Dryer
Source: [5]

During the design of the dryer [2, 6,7], some considerations were made for the effective operation of the dryer. These considerations are presented below

i) The amount of moisture removed (M_R):

The amount of moisture that will be removed from the clay in the dryer is calculated using Equation 1.

$$M_R = M_W \left[\left(\frac{Q_1 - Q_2}{100 - Q_2} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

Where

M_R is mass of moisture removed from sample (kg);

M_W is mass of wet or dry sample (kg);

Q_1 is initial Moisture content (%);

Q_2 is the final moisture content on experimental results (%)

M_D is $M_W - M_R$ while M_D is weight of dried sample (kg)

ii) Volume of Air to effect drying: The volume of air required to dry the clay sample is given in Equation 3.

$$Q_A = \left[\left(\frac{M_R}{H_{R1} - H_{R2}} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

$$V_A = \left[\left(\frac{Q_A}{\gamma_A} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

Where Q_A is quantity of heat to effect drying (kg), V_A is volume of air to effect drying (m^3)

H_{R1} is initial humidity ratio in kg/kg dry air 0.01 kg/kg dry air using the psychometric chart under normal temperature and 101.325 kPa barometric pressure where ambient temperature and relative humidity are 32 °C and 35 % respectively.

H_{R2} is final humidity ratio in kg/kg dry air 0.027 kg/kg after been supplied when temperature rises to 40 °C, γ_A is the density of air in is 1.115 kg^{-3} at 0°C based o the properties of common fluids.

The dryer tray Dimension was 0.241 m by 0.330 m which gave an area of 0.0795 m^2 .

The control panel dimension is 0.254 m by 0.152 m which gave an area of 0.0386 m^2

iii) Performance equation: The performance equation [8,9,10] of the dryer was calculated using Equations 4 to 10.

Thermal efficiency η_c of the dryer [11]

The thermal efficiency of the dryer was calculated using Equation 4.

$$\eta_c = \frac{H_D}{t \times Q_{ht}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Where H_D is the quantity of heat used in effecting drying (kJ), Q_{ht} is the heat transfer (kJ) and t is the drying time, which was between 4 to 6 hrs.

Drying rate R_c of clay/Zeolite

The drying rate of clay and Zeolite was calculated using Equation 5.

$$R_c = \left(\frac{M_D}{A_s} \right) \left(\frac{Q_1 - Q_2}{t} \right) \quad (5)$$

Where R_c is the drying rate (kg/mol), A_s is the surface area of dried sample (m^2), M_D is the weight of dried sample (kg), t is the optimum drying time, 27.5hrs, Q_1 is the initial moisture content (%), and Q_2 is the final moisture content (%)

Quantity of heat required to remove moisture content

The quantity of heat required to remove moisture from clay sample was calculated using Equation 6

$$Q_t = M_R C_p \Delta T + M_R H_{fg} \quad (6)$$

where Q_t is the quantity of heat to raise temperature to say 83 °C required to remove moisture, C_p is the specific heat capacity of water (4.182 KJ/kg °C), H_{fg} is the heat of evaporation (2405.9 KJ/Kg at 83 °C) ΔT is the temperature difference between dried samples and initial temperature of the of the drier assuming the dryer initially was 35 °C and experimental temperature was at 83 °C (83 – 35) 48 °C; to calculate the power of heating element, Power = $Q_t / time$ was used.

Fan Capacity (FC)

The fan serves the purpose of transferring the heated air from the heater to the drying chamber, The fan capacity was calculated using Equation 3.7.

$$FC = Q_A - Q_N (n) \quad (7)$$

Where Q_N is $r_a \times q_2$, Q_N is the air flow rate. (kg/min), r_a is the density of air which was taken as 1.115 kg/m^3 , q_2 is the volumetric flow rate (m^3/min) and (n) is the percentage safety factor; that ensure an adequate supply of air in all operating condition at 15 % but usually 10-20 % can be used.

Conductive heat loss through the fan to the air

Heat loss by the fan was calculated using Equation 8.

$$q_L = \frac{KAT_{BE}}{\delta_k} \quad (8)$$

Where q_L is the quantity of heat lost (kJ), δ_k is the constant which was taken as 1, A is the surface area of the fan, (m^2), K is the thermal conductivity of mild steel which was 58 w/mK , T_{BE} is the temperature difference between hot air in the blower and the environment was calculated as $83-35$ which gave $48 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Heat to effect drying H_D of Clay

The heat to effect drying was calculated as shown in Equation 3.9

$$H_D = C_a T_C M_R V_C \quad (9)$$

Where C_a is the specific heat capacity of air, which was taken as $1.005 \text{ kJ/kg}^\circ\text{C}$, T_C is the temperature difference in the dryer ($80-32$) = $48 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, V_C is the volume of drying chamber (m^3)

Rate of heat transfer Q_{mtr} from moist clay to the atmosphere

The rate of heat transfer from the moist clay in the dryer to the atmosphere was calculated using Equation 10.

$$Q_{mtr} = M_c A_t (H_{R1} - H_{R2}) q_2 \quad (10)$$

where M_c is the mass transfer [12] coefficient of free water surface, $0.083 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$, A_t is the total surface area of the 2 trays inside the dryer (m^2), H_{R1} is the initial humidity ratio in kg/kg dry air 0.028 kg/kg

H_{R2} is the final humidity ratio (kg/kg) dry air 0.01 and q_2 is the air flow rate, (m^3/sec)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Aspen Plus version 11 was used to simulate the design [1,13,14,15,16] process with known parameters (from laboratory results-some of which are shown in Table 1).

Table 1. Results of X-ray Fluorescence (XRF) Analysis of Raw and Beneficiated, Udung Uko kaolin

Chemical Constituent	Raw Clay Mole %	Beneficiated Mole %	Dry Mole %
SiO ₂	84.64	72.90	72.90
Al ₂ O ₃	7.38	10.91	10.91
CaO	0.76	4.66	4.66

SO ₃	0.65	1.69	1.69
K ₂ O	1.24	1.56	1.56
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.57	2.05	2.05
TiO ₂	1.77	3.35	3.35
Cl	2.95	2.84	2.84
Moisture Content		60%	20%

Source: [17,18]

A series of computations and concepts of basic engineering were performed.

3.0 kilograms batch of raw kaolinite clay (kaolin) from Udung Uko in Akwa Ibom State was used for the simulation.

The reaction set and simulation strategy during the processes are presented below:

(A) The reaction set:

(i) Dryer

There are changes that occur when kaolin is heated in the dryer. The reaction series include the formation of highly disordered metakaolin formed at about 550-900⁰C ,However for drying [6,18,19,20] the reaction is as shown in the Equation 11:

B) Simulation set

Figure 3. Dryer Simulation

The mass balance across the dryer generated during the simulation is given in Table 2 below. A2 is the heated air blowing across the wet Kaolinite material (WET K) in the drying chamber while A3 is the air out of the dryer. DRY K is the dried Kaolin.

Table 2. Mass Balance Across the Dryer

	MASS IN		MASS OUT	
	(kg/hr)		(kg/hr)	
	A2	WET-K	A3	DRY-K
WATER	0.0000	0.1706	0.1431	0.0275
AIR	5.0000	0.0000	5.0000	0.0000
KAOLIN	0.0000	2.5821	0.0000	2.5821
POTAS. OXIDE	0.0000	0.0122	0.0000	0.0122
ANATASE	0.0000	0.0301	0.0000	0.0301

HEMATITE	0.0000	0.0162	0.0000	0.0162
MUSCOVIT	0.0000	0.0048	0.0000	0.0048
SiO_2	0.0000	0.0250	0.0000	0.0250
FELDSPAR	0.0000	0.0006	0.0000	0.0006
PYRITE	0.0000	0.0003	0.0000	0.0003
V_2O_5	0.0000	0.0014	0.0000	0.0014
Total	5.0000	2.8435	5.1431	2.7004
Grand Total	7.8435		7.8435	

The fabrication, electrical connections and finished work are shown in Figures 4a to 4c.

Dryer Fabrication (a)

Dryer Fabrication (b)

Figure 4a. Dryer Fabrication with door closed (a) and opened (b)
Source: [7]

Figure 4b. Dryer Fabrication and Connections

Figure 4c. Fabricated Dryer

Advantages of This Dryer and Standard Operating Procedure (SOP)

Some advantages of this equipment and SOP are reported in this section

- a. The heating temperature and fan speed can be regulated; (The regulation of the fan speed is an unusual approach to our design; thus, it is novel).
- b. The door screw lock available to minimize heat loss and hermitization (isolating the dryer from atmospheric interference);
- c. Convenient design allows to remove trays, thereby making it possible to use the cabinet for other operation: heating, hardening, baking etc.
- d. The heating elements can get up to 300°C, allowing to extend the range of chamber application;
- e. Developed standard operating procedure (SOP) to protect the user from maloperation and accidents.

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) and cleaning of the Dryer

i) SOP

- a. Before starting the dryer, it is required that users put on personal protective equipment (PPE), check that the dryer is clean, dry and in a well-ventilated environment (to ensure free access to air inlet and outlet).
- b. load the materials onto the trays and close the door firmly.
- c. turn on the electrical supply, then start the blower and heater by setting the temperature to say 45°C, and timer for 3 hours
- d. allow the fan to run until dryer temperature is about 28°C,
- e. open the door, remove the trays with appropriate PPE and close the door
- f. turn off the blower and turned off the power supply.

ii) Cleaning the dryer: To clean the dryer.it is required that users:

- a. ensure that the dryer is in a cold state. Avoid cleaning the dryer when it is hot.

- b. ensure the correct personal protective equipment such as hand gloves, dust mask etc is worn
- c. turn off the tray dryer switch. (Opened the electric power breaker)
- d. get a dry duster to remove the dust on the body of the dryer cabinet.
- e. remove all the trays inside and placed them in the washing area.
- f. ensure that all of the dried Zeolite material in the drying chamber is removed.
- g. cleaned each tray with potable water and clean with a suitable surfactant followed by deionized water.
- h. dry all trays with a dry cloth.

In case of any fault or incidence, it is advisable to call/contact the technician [20,21,22]

The cost of design and Fabrication was two hundred and fifty-four thousand four hundred and fifty naira only

(₦254,450). The details of the Bill of Engineering Measurement and Evaluation (BEME) for the design and fabrication of an electric Zeolite/Clay/Bentonite dryer are as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Bill of Engineering Measurement and Evaluation (BEME) for the Design and Fabrication of an Electric Zeolite/Clay Dryer

S/N	Description	Material and sizes	Quantity	Rate (₦)	Cost (₦)
1	Mild steel plate (grade 304)	2mm*1220*610	0.5	70,000	35,000
2	Screws/control panel plates				4,500
3	Adjustable speed dc brushless electric fan (model ffb0612ehe)	12V DC,1.2a,5090rpm	1	3,000	3,000
4	Electric ac cable	1.5mm*3 cores	2.5 meters	1000	2,500
5	Plug/switches	15 amps/100amps	1	3700	3700
6	Electric heat-resistant cable	4mm (single core)	1.5 meters	1,500	2,250
7	Digital thermometer	C100fk02-m*an	1	24,000	24,000
	Ally timer	Ah3-3	1	10,000	10,000
8	Thermocouple		1	8,000	8,000
9	Contactora	telemecanique bs5424	1	28,000	28,000
10	Transformer	15v	1	13,000	13,000
11	Bolts, washes, rivet pins, hinges and nuts	Steel m10*1.25	10	200	2,000
12	Electrode	Gauge 12	1 packet	12,000	12,000
13	Insulation material	2-inch thickness		20,000	20,000
14	Paint	4 litres	1	5,500	5,500
15	Trays	Galvanized 20mm*50	2	2,000	4,000
16	Mild steel angle bar, hinges and square pipes (half and 2 inch)	2mm*50*50	2	3,000	6,000
17	2kw heating element		1	24,000	24,000
18	Circuit components (fan switch and dc-ac conversion)				12,000
19	Workmanship/labour				30,000
20	Transportation and miscellaneous				5,000
21	Grand total				254,450

Note: 1 US Dollar equals 1570.57 Nigerian naira (₦)

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria, December, 2024, exchange rate-US dollar. <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/rates/ExchRateByCurrency.html>

RESULTS

Wet samples of Kaolin at ambient temperature were taken and dried in the dryer at 750 rpm, 250 degrees Celsius for two hours and the result are as shown in Figure 5 and Table 1,

Moisture content was calculated to have reduced from 60 to 20 percent using equation 1

Before drying:

Weight of plate: 400g

Weight of sample on plate: 1125g

Fan Speed: 750rpm

Temperature: 28 degrees Celsius (Ambient)

Time: 0 hours

After drying:

Weight of plate: 400g

Weight of sample on plate :930g

Fan Speed: 750rpm

Temperature: 250 degrees Celsius

Time: 2 hours

Figure 5. Samples (before and after drying)

DISCUSSION

As illustrated in the Figure 3, the conceptual design was followed through the principles of dryer (Figure 2) and the various equations leading to the fabrication of the dryer. In Table 1 samples of kaolin were analyzed for simulation and the reaction set including mass balance across the dryer was captured (Table 2)

The electrical connections to facilitate maintenance and reproducibility. Wet samples of Kaolin at ambient temperature were taken and dried in the dryer at 750 rpm, 250 degrees Celsius for two hours and the result are as shown in Figure 5 and Table 1,

Moisture content was calculated to have reduced from 60 to 20 percent using equation 1 as shown in Figure 5

CONCLUSION

The design and fabrication of a specialized dryer for Zeolite synthesis represent a significant advancement in the field of material processing. This study has successfully demonstrated that by tailoring the drying equipment to the specific needs of Zeolite production, efficiency in the synthesis process can be greatly enhanced. The custom dryer developed offers controlled drying environments, which is crucial for maintaining the structural integrity and maximizing the adsorption

capacity of Zeolites. Moreover, the engineering solution proposed in this work not only optimizes the drying process but also contributes to local technology in industrial applications. The integration of advanced drying technologies [23] ensures that the Zeolite products meet the high-quality standards required for various applications, including catalysis, gas separation and environmental remediation [24,25].

Overall, this work underscores the importance of equipment customization in the material processing industry, paving the way for further innovations in Zeolite production and beyond. The successful implementation of this dryer design can serve as a model for future engineering projects aimed at enhancing the performance and sustainability of industrial processes.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Ceballos, E. Devic, and J. Lozano, "Design and performance of a novel hybrid solar dryer for small-scale agricultural operations," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 157, pp. 319–329, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2020.05.036.
- [2] M. Karmakar and R. Banerjee, "Recent advances in industrial drying systems: A comprehensive review," *Drying Technology*, vol. 35, no. 13, pp. 1585–1597, 2017. DOI: 10.1080/07373937.2017.1284691.
- [3] H. Zhang and Y. Xu, "Advances in additive manufacturing for drying equipment components," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 762, p. 138097, 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.msea.2019.138097.
- [4] T. B. Onifade, A. Taiwo, and S. O. Jekayinfa, "Modification of a locally made electric crop dryer," *Innovative Systems Design and Engineering*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 40–51, 2016. Available: <https://www.iiste.org>.
- [5] A. Efendi, A. Nugraha, and R. Baharta, "Manufacturing of electrical dryer machine for food and fruit products," in *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 547, pp. 1–7, 2019. DOI: 10.1088/1757-899X/547/1/012009.
- [6] L. Zhang and H. Li, "Heat transfer analysis in drying equipment design: Recent developments and challenges," *Journal of Heat Transfer*, vol. 144, no. 6, p. 061303, 2022. DOI: 10.1115/1.4052833
- [7] C.N Egwu, R Babalola, T.H Udoh and E.O Oboho (2022), Design and Fabrication of an Electric Furnace for the Calcination of Kaolinite Clay to Metakaolin. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research* Volume 13, Issue 4, ISSN 2229-5518. 1224-1232, 2022.
- [8] V. Dhaka and A. Shukla, "Development and performance evaluation of a photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) integrated solar dryer," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 120, pp. 169–179, 2018. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2017.12.073.
- [9] A. Buonomano, A. Palombo, and L. Santini, "Solar-assisted dryers: A review of their performance and applications," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 178, pp. 326–351, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2021.06.122.
- [10] Uzono R.I, Ojong O.E Mathematical Modelling of Operating Temperature Variations of Shell-and-Tube Heat Exchanger (10-E-01) *World Journal of Engineering and Technology* 10 (2), 422-433,2022
- [11] W. Song and S. Zhang, "Innovations in materials for drying equipment to enhance thermal efficiency," *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 83, pp. 448–458, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.jmapro.2023.01.019.

- [12] E. O Ojong, V.I Etim, G.E.E Aquah, R.I Uzono Design and Simulation of the Major Units of Acetone Plant from Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA) Route. *Advances in Science and Technology* 142, 171-180,2024
- [13] Y. Fan and J. Lee, "Convective drying technology: A comprehensive review of mathematical modeling," *Drying Technology*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 763–783, 2018. DOI: 10.1080/07373937.2017.1350843.
- [14] A. Sharma and G. Chen, "Development and validation of a computational model for freeze-drying," *Drying Technology*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 1189–1202, 2022. DOI: 10.1080/07373937.2021.1923623.
- [15] X. Chen and X. Hu, "Thermodynamic analysis and optimization of drying processes," *Applied Thermal Engineering*, vol. 221, p. 119882, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2022.119882.
- [16] Y. Zhao, M. Zhang, S. Devahastin, and X. Yang, "Advances in drying technology for sustainable food processing," *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, vol. 128, pp. 43–56, 2022. DOI: 10.1016/j.tifs.2022.07.002.
- [17] W. Lutz, Y. Zhang, and K. A. Rosentrater, "Dryer design considerations for enhanced performance in food processing," *Drying Technology*, vol. 39, no. 9, pp. 1327–1340, 2021. DOI: 10.1080/07373937.2020.1845373.
- [18] O.O Okwonna, I.J Otaraku, K.M Oduola, E.O Okeke Study of the Effect of Attrition on the Properties of Catalyst Used for Industrial FCC Operation. *Int J Eng Sci Invent* 8 (7), 53-66,2019
- [19] N. Dhakal and R. Bhattarai, "Fabrication techniques for energy-efficient dryers: A review," *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, vol. 30, pp. 327–342, 2017. DOI: 10.1016/j.jmapro.2017.08.003.
- [20] A. Khalil and N. Shaari, "Hybrid drying systems: A review of design and operational challenges," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 107, pp. 333–348, 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.rser.2019.03.024.
- [21] X. Jin and X. Gao, "Advanced drying technologies for pharmaceutical applications: A review," *Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, vol. 112, no. 2, pp. 546–557, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.xphs.2022.10.003.
- [22] "Operation and cleaning of tray dryer," *Pharmaguide*, 2011. Available: <https://www.pharmaguideline.com/2011/04/operation-and-cleaning-of-tray-dryer.html>.
- [23] U. Pal and A. Singh, "Application of microwave-assisted drying technologies in food processing: A review," *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, vol. 57, no. 5, pp. 1354–1366, 2020. DOI: 10.1007/s13197-019-04186-2.
- [24] C. Ratti and A. S. Mujumdar, "Advances in drying technologies for agricultural products: A comprehensive review," *Journal of Food Engineering*, vol. 307, p. 110685, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2021.110685.
- [25] A. Kharaghani and M. Akbari, "Heat and mass transfer in porous media during drying: A comprehensive review," *International Journal of Thermal Sciences*, vol. 112, pp. 169–182, 2017. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijthermalsci.2016.10.020.

